

**PEDAGOGICAL AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN THE
ACTIVITY OF A MUSIC TEACHER**

Tursunaliyeva Mukhlisakhan Vokhidjon kizi

Andijan State University

Teacher of the Department of Music Education, Faculty of Arts

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117816>

Abstract: In this article, there are opinions about the pedagogical and communicative abilities of a music teacher, their types and their importance in the field.

Key words. Music, pedagogy, personal qualities, professional qualities, communication, communication.

Ability is one of the most important characteristics of the human psyche, and the relative weakness of some ability due to the possibility of filling these characteristics too widely, even with this ability, there is no possibility of successful performance of activities that are closely related to each other. not no. Abilities are not reflected in knowledge, skills and qualifications, but in the dynamics of their acquisition. The differences that arise in the process of acquiring the knowledge and skills necessary for the activity make it possible to think about abilities. Therefore, the individual psychological characteristic that is considered a condition for the successful implementation of a person's activities, manifested in differences in the dynamics of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, is called abilities.

Pedagogical ability is one of the types of ability that determines a person's suitability for pedagogical activity and the ability to successfully engage in this activity. In pedagogical psychology, effective studies have been conducted on the scientific explanation of the role of pedagogical skills in teaching activities.

Pedagogical scientist I.P. Podlasi defined the structure of pedagogical ability as follows:

- organization,
- diagnostic,
- perceptive,
- communicative,
- convince
- about research,
- about scientific knowledge,
- gnostic.

Based on the scientific research conducted in the field of pedagogy and psychology, in our opinion, the teacher's pedagogical abilities can be classified as follows:

- ✚ didactic ability,
- ✚ academic ability,
- ✚ perceptual ability,
- ✚ speaking ability,
- ✚ organizational skills,
- ✚ the ability to have a reputation,
- ✚ communication skills,

- ✚ psychological diagnosis (diagnosis) skills,
- ✚ ability to divide attention,
- ✚ constructive ability,
- ✚ gnostic ability.

Pedagogical skills are related to teacher's character-qualities. Organization, strictness, and honesty lead to an increase in the level of pedagogical activity, on the contrary, disorganization, complacency, and injustice reduce the effectiveness of pedagogical activity.

Professional activity combines several components as a whole system. I.P. Based on Podlasi's classification of the structure of professional potential, N.M. Egamberdiyeva distinguishes the following important structural components of professional maturity (professionalization), socialization, humanization, and cultural creativity in pedagogical education, which are in accordance with modern trends:

- pedagogical culture;
- creativity of the teacher;
- pedagogical intelligence;
- possession of deep professional knowledge;
- individual activity style;
- development of creative initiative;
- individual activity;
- orientation to humanitarianism;
- social activity.

Communicative ability is the ability to communicate, which has a special appearance in the field of pedagogical interaction. Several types of communicative abilities are distinguished in psychological literature:

- 1) a person's ability to understand a person,
- 2) a person's self-awareness,
- 3) the ability to correctly assess the communication situation.

The main methods of pedagogical influence by the teacher in the process of education and training include: demand, perspective, encouragement and punishment, public opinion. The socio-psychological theory of communication and the study of pedagogical experiences show that two methods should be widely used in pedagogical influence: persuasion and persuasion.

Any kind of educational influence of the teacher, as a result, it is not possible to have an all-round influence on the psyche of the student, that is, to form and strengthen positive emotions in students: behavior, attitudes, behavior. will complain. But the technological mechanisms of persuasion and transmission are different. Growing young people interact with the social environment and nature. As a result of this interaction, trust, new knowledge and relationships, and a set of moral standards are created in them.

It is necessary for a teacher to have pedagogical knowledge, creativity, and reflection, as well as master pedagogical culture. Pedagogical culture from a professional point of view is a component of the general culture of a specialist who carries out pedagogical activities.

In conclusion, it can be said that the teacher's pedagogical ability and communicative ability occupy an important place in education and training. Today's youth should be fully developed, able to express their right attitude to themselves, other people, society, nature and work, be able to work independently, be creative, enterprising and entrepreneurs. The

development of these characteristics in the student depends on the teacher's ability to properly manage the educational process and the relationships he can establish with the students.

References:

- 1.Sh.M. Mirziyoev. "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people". Tashkent "Uzbekistan"-2017.
- 2.Akhmedova M.T. Pedagogical competence. - T.: TDRU named after Nizami, 2016. - 84 p.
- 3.Ashurov A.A. The concept of communicative competence and its essence //Foreign languages in Uzbekistan. – 2020. – No. 1(30). 76–83b.
- 4.Panjiev Q.B., Salimova D.I. "Vocals and modern music". Tashkent.
5. Musaeva, N. S., & Khamidova, M. P. (2020). Speech development in elementary school students and ways to develop vocabulary. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, 24(6), 289-296.
- 6.Muslimov N.A. Problems of a systematic approach to pedagogical activity // Vocational education. - 2004. - No. 3. - B.24.